

NFDI4Chem, Chemistry Consortium in the NFDI

Deliverable D4.1.2
Guidance Document on MICH

TA4 – Metadata, Data Standards and Publication Standards

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of the NFDI4Chem activities in Measure 4.1 to develop standards for *Minimum Information about a Chemical Investigation* (MICH) for diverse methods and sub-disciplines of chemistry to render data FAIR for humans and machines. This goal can be achieved by:

- providing the MICHs as checklist and guideline article,
- incorporating controlled vocabulary-derived term definitions and acceptable values whenever possible, with proper linking to the controlled vocabularies,
- providing human and machine-readable examples,
- integrating persistent identifiers, particularly for chemical substances, ensuring longevity and traceability,
- hosting international workshops, including international standardisation organisations such as IUPAC, to solidify the global collaborative effort in MICH standardisation and acceptance, and
- maintaining open drafts available for public review and comment by the global chemistry community, promoting transparency and inclusiveness.

These endeavours involve the concerted efforts of TA2 *Smart Lab*, TA3 *Repositories*, and TA4 *Metadata, Data Standards and Publication Standards* of NFDI4Chem to gather and assess chemical metadata. Additionally, TA6 plays a pivotal role in providing the terminology service¹ and enhancing controlled vocabularies essential for the MICHs.

Project Objectives

This deliverable has contributed particularly to **Objective 4.1** of TA4 to provide a set of coherent and interoperable data standards. Moreover, this deliverable has contributed and *will continue to contribute* to the following key objectives in NFDI4Chem²:

Key Objective 2 to initiate international community processes to establish minimum information (MI) standards for data and machine-readable metadata as well as open data standards in key areas of chemistry. Identify and recommend open data standards in key areas of chemistry, in order to support the FAIR principles for research data.

Key Objective 4 to engage with the chemistry community in Germany to create awareness for, and foster the adoption of FAIR data management and to offer information materials for researchers.

Key Objective 6 to provide a framework of policies and guidelines for FAIR research data management.

¹ P. Strömert, V. Limbachia, P. Oladazimi, J. Hunold, O. Koepler. Towards a Versatile Terminology Service for Empowering FAIR Research Data: Enabling Ontology Discovery, Design, Curation, and Utilization Across Scientific Communities, *IOS Press* **2023**, 56, 53-69, DOI: [10.3233/SSW230005](https://doi.org/10.3233/SSW230005). NFDI4Chem Terminology Service. URL: <https://terminology.nfdi4chem.de/>.

² C. Steinbeck, O. Koepler, F. Bach, S. Herres-Pawlis, N. Jung, J. C. Liermann, S. Neumann, M. Razum, C. Baldauf, F. Biedermann, T. W. Bocklitz, F. Boehm, F. Broda, P. Czodrowski, T. Engel, M. G. Hicks, S. M. Kast, C. Kettner, W. Koch, G. Lanza, A. Link, R. A. Mata, W. E. Nagel, A. Porzel, N. Schlörer, T. Schulze, H.-G. Weinig, W. Wenzel, L. A. Wessjohann, S. Wulle, NFDI4Chem - Towards a National Research Data Infrastructure for Chemistry in Germany, *RIO* **2020**, 6, e55852, DOI: [10.3897/rio.6.e55852](https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.6.e55852).

Detailed Report on The Deliverable

Background

This deliverable is part of the activities in Measure 4.1 *Development of Minimum Information metadata standards for Chemical Investigations*, which requires iterative discussions, and ensuring human and machine-readability. The process needs in-depth expertise in addition to open communication with the chemistry community to receive reviews and comments to improve acceptance. The objective of this deliverable is to define a MICH standard through consensus and which allow humans and machines to reuse and interpret data.³

Description of Work

The primary task in MICH development is to create and publish a guidance document with concrete recommendations about *Minimum Information about a Chemical Investigation* (MICH), based on a broad consensus. Given the intricate nature of this task, the approach involves a multifaceted strategy:

1. Stakeholders and previous works:
 - Community and standardisation bodies: A thorough examination of existing data and metadata standards was conducted to enable the reuse of existing standards and to ensure alignment with current practices.
 - Publishers: Existing recommendations by academic publishers are examined and considered.
 - Analytical instrument manufacturers: Existing vendor data and metadata standards are considered.
 - Infrastructure: Evaluation of existing and in-development research data infrastructure that handles and extracts metadata is considered.
2. Community involvement:
 - Workshops: Active engagement in extensive discussions with the community via workshops to incorporate diverse perspectives into the standards development process and to set the foundations for a global collaborative effort in MICH standardisation and acceptance.
 - Requests for comments by the wider chemistry community: Maintaining open drafts available for public review and comment to promote transparency and inclusiveness, and to ensure global acceptance of the MICH standard.

³ S. Herres-Pawlis, F. Bach, I. J. Bruno, S. J. Chalk, N. Jung, J. C. Liermann, L. R. McEwen, S. Neumann, C. Steinbeck, M. Razum, O. Koepler, Minimum Information Standards in Chemistry: A Call for Better Research Data Management Practices, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2022, 61, 51, e202203038, DOI: [10.1002/anie.202203038](https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202203038).

MICHl Structure

We have designed the MICHl structure including its sub-elements (Figure 1) to be reusable by researchers, applicable by publishers, infrastructure developers and instrument manufacturers, and supportive of machine-readability. The structure includes the following sub-elements:

- **Guideline article:** Is a textual description and is aimed at the broader scientific community to introduce the respective MICHl, delineate its scope and coverage, and provide the overall content. It is intended for dissemination through academic publishers as well as repositories to the target audience and can also be used for training.
- **Checklist:** It comprises a list of the specific information to be reported, possibly accompanied by a brief explanation and examples. This checklist can serve as supporting material in the guideline article and also in author guidelines of scientific journals.
- **Data model:** It is targeted at software and infrastructure developers to facilitate the implementation of software or data exchange formats for creating, managing, validating, publishing, and archiving chemical research data. It encompasses modelling all objects and relations relevant to describe the data effectively.

FAIR Data Principles			
Output	Guideline Article	Checklist	Data Model
Description	textual, human readable description	brief, human readable list	definition of objects and relations to allow standard implementation
Form	article	list/table	formal language, UML models/class diagrams
Main Targets	researchers	researchers, academic publishers	infrastructure developers, instrument manufacturers

Controlled Vocabularies and Ontologies

Figure 1: Recommended structure of Minimum Information about a Chemical Investigation (MICHl) standards including a guideline article, checklist and an initial data model.

Controlled vocabularies and ontologies enhance machine-readability and also provide reference for humans on term definitions. We recommend using existing controlled vocabularies and avoiding the creation of new ones unless necessary.

FAIRness, Digitalisation, and Machine-Readability

In the formulation of our standards, we adhere to the FAIR principles⁴. To achieve this, we employ identifiers to ensure that data aligned with our recommendations can easily be findable. Moreover, we focus on (existing) controlled vocabularies whenever possible to enhance semantic interoperability. By targeting infrastructures such as ELNs and repositories with our recommendations, and by providing such platforms that facilitate compliance, we aspire to augment data accessibility, while also targeting analytical software developers, especially the ones generating the raw files, and standardising the included metadata and its representation can significantly enhance interoperability. In the same context, controlled vocabularies play a key role in interoperability and machine-readability.

Ultimately, our goal is to maximise the reusability of data, and the provision of MICHl serves as a foundational step towards it. Each MICHl will be published under an open access licence to allow for reuse of that MICHl.

Risks and Mitigation

Minimum Information standards such as MICHls can be thought of as the final destinations of a long road including several steps of building a clear tree structure of a chemistry field and its analytical methods, securing established identifiers and controlled vocabulary there, and garnering community acceptance. The absence of identifiers and controlled vocabularies can easily lead discussions on Minimum Information astray, particularly when granularity levels within the field are unclear. Selecting the appropriate level of modularity to cover field requirements while avoiding branching at the same time is not a trivial task. An effective approach involves initiating the building process from a fine level to then gradually expanding, identifying shared metadata with other branches. Furthermore, we need to consider that the process of revision can be inherently time-consuming when planning the development of a robust MICHl standard.

Furthermore, there is a need for additional efforts in refining the controlled vocabularies to be utilised. Restricting their number may streamline the implementation of MICHls in repositories by minimising dependencies.

Next Steps

The next steps include work on the individual MICHls for diverse analytical methods used in chemical sciences. Having a MICHl in hand, will enable further efforts to enhance analytical data format standards for exchange and archival, and finally to build software components for the creation, validation and conversion of such standardised formats.

⁴ FAIR Data Principles, GoFair, URL: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.